

**PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND THE IMPLEMENTATION
OF ESTACODE IN NIGERIA DURING PRESIDENT MOHAMMADU
BUHARI ADMINISTRATION (2015 - 2023)**

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Abstract

The study delves into the most challenging issues the government encountered, including the abuses perpetrated by stakeholders at the national, state, and local levels during the implementation of the approved remuneration package, which served as a standard for political, public, and judicial office holders. The pineapple theory of equitable but shrewd distribution of government resources propounded by Unwana-Abasi Udoh in 2023 was adopted, while qualitative survey research design with secondary data from books, journals, newspapers, and the internet. The ex-post facto research design and content analysis were adopted for data analyses. Two subsidiary objectives were set, including to find out whether there were challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders. The first of the two research questions asked was: Were there challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders? Two null (H_0) hypotheses were postulated, among which include: There appears to have been no challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political,

public, and judicial office holders. Out of the two findings made, the first showed that there had been challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders. Based on the findings, it was first recommended that the federal government should set up machinery that will resolve all the challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders.

Keywords: Public Financial Management, Administration, Implementation, Estacode, Mohammadu Buhari administration.

1. Background to the study

One may be lost in the dictionary or may spend precious time in vain searching for the term "estacode." Estacode is not an English word, and as such, it would not be found in the dictionary. It may also not be provided in Google. Estacode is a term used in government, especially in the context of international travel allowances. It refers to the daily allowance or stipend provided to public officials who travel outside their usual work location, typically to another city or country. According to data from the Revenue Mobilisation, Allocation, and Fiscal Commission (RMAFC, 2021), Nigeria's political, public, and judicial office holders receive a combined sum of \$24,385 as estacode for every night they spend traveling. The data revealed that the Chief Justice of Nigeria gets the highest pay with \$2,000 per night, followed by the Justice of the Supreme Court, Appeal Court President, and Senate President with \$1,300 each. RMAFC had said public office holders often abused the remuneration package, leading to the commission being criticised for fixing high amounts for allowances. "Perhaps the most challenging issue the Commission faces is the abuse by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package for political, public, and judicial office holders," the commission stated. Keyamo (2015) is worried about the bad impression that the public is holding about the fixing of jumbo pay to the beneficiaries by the commission. "This has left the general public with the impression that the Commission fixed jumbo pay for political, public, and judicial office holders in spite of several clarifications by the Commission in the media on the matter.

On a final note, an abridged overview of public finance by Atkinson *et al.* (1980) holds that public finance is the study of the role of the government in the economy. It is the branch of economics that assesses government revenue and expenditure by

public authorities and adjusts one or the other to achieve desirable effects while avoiding undesirable ones (Udoh, 2018). But Buchanan (1987) in Udoh (2018) has provided the purview of public finance as being considered to be threefold, consisting of governmental effects on: the efficient allocation of available resources; the distribution of income among citizens; and the stability of the economy.

It is, however, based on the foregoing that this research was set to unravel public financial management and the implementation of estacode in Nigeria during the President Muhammadu Buhari Administration (2015 and 2023), which specifically bothered on the most challenging issues the government faced, such as the abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders.

2. Statement of the problem

The inadequate application of estacode in Nigeria has resulted in the exploitation of foreign travels, which are intended to be journeys undertaken in countries other than one's own. However, the government had the most difficult problems in dealing with the misconduct of individuals involved in the administration of the authorised remuneration package, known as an estacode, for political, public, and judicial officials at the national, state, and local government levels. In Nigeria, the government and corporate sector have consistently offered lodging for foreign travel to incentivise residents to participate in international conferences, meetings, seminars, and similar events. Some individuals independently travel overseas for purposes such as holidays, medical treatment, and various other reasons. However, as a result of the inadequate state of healthcare facilities in Nigeria, numerous affluent Nigerians, both in the public and private sectors, have opted to travel outside to countries such as the UK, Britain, London, and India to fulfil their healthcare requirements. Estacode is a form of compensation provided to government officials and private sector employees when they travel abroad for official purposes. The purpose of this research is to identify the most pressing issues faced by the government and the misconduct by stakeholders at the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package for political, public, and judicial office holders. The aim is to find solutions to these challenges.

Regrettably, in Nigeria, when a means of profiting from the government is established or uncovered, a significant majority of the population will seek to take advantage of it. Udoh et al. (2019) have identified the extent of exploitation inflicted upon Nigeria's economy by stakeholders as a significant and worrisome issue. The statement made by Odum (2003) in Udoh et al. (2017) suggests that in contemporary

politics, the focus has shifted from ideas to money, and actions that reflect a constant diversity of ideologies have become a fundamental aspect of political discourse. As previously mentioned in the study's context, estacode has become a lucrative method for Nigerian government personnel to earn money. This has raised concerns among both academics and media. This negates Ime T. Akpan's idea of public financial management while writing Nwaeze's (2009) foreword, as reported in Udoh et al. (2018), as noting that its topical and sensitive objectives "are to ensure that public monies are frugally managed according to laid-down principles."

3. The study's objectives

The study's objectives include both the main objective and the subsidiary objectives.

The main objective

The main objective of this research is to examine public financial management and the implementation of estacode in Nigeria during the President Muhammadu Buhari administration between 2015 and 2023.

Subsidiary objectives:

The subsidiary objectives of the study include:

1. To find out whether there were challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders.
2. To verify the level of implementation of estacode in Nigeria during the President Muhammadu Buhari administration between 2015 and 2023.

4. Research questions

The following questions were asked to enable the researcher to elicit responses from respondents:

- i. Were there challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders?
- ii. What was the level of Estacode implementation in Nigeria during President Muhammadu Buhari's administration, between 2015 and 2023?

5. Research hypotheses

Two null (H₀) hypotheses were postulated to enable the researcher to test the opinions of respondents and also carry out empirical investigations in the study. These include:

- i. H₀: There appears to have been no challenging issues that the government

- faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders.
- ii. H0: The level of implementation of estacode in Nigeria during the President Mohammadu Buhari administration between 2015 and 2023 tended to have been very high.

Definition of terms

Public finance management

According to Udoh (2022), "public financial management is pivotal or paramount in all spheres of economic endeavours in our contemporary society today." Similarly, public financial management (PFM) is a central element of a functioning administration, underlying all government activities. It encompasses the mechanisms through which public resources are collected, allocated, spent, and accounted for (Udoh, 2024).

Administration

In Udoh (2014), Luther Gurlick and Lindall Urwick presumed that "Public administration is public administration, anywhere it was found". The scholars made the presumption in their "Papers on the Science of Administration" while studying administrative management. Gurlick and Urwick devoted their energies to the discovery of "principles" of management that could be applied anywhere. While working under President Roosevelt of the United States of America, they concluded that "once an administrative principle was found, it logically should work in any kind of administrative institution: government bureaucracies, universities, etc.—wherever. Thus, in 1937, Gurlick and Urwick gave us POSDCORS" as an anagram in public administration. Whereas Pfiffner Prethus (1967), cited in Udoh (2014), defined administration as the coordination of collective efforts to implement public policy. That is a collective affair involving many people, and it should benefit the majority.

Estacode

Estacode is a term used in government, especially in the context of international travel allowances. It refers to the daily allowance or stipend provided to public officials who travel outside their usual work location, typically to another city or country. But, in Nigeria, "Estacode" refers to a form of travel allowance given to government officials. As usual, we've left out the entire meaning of the word when making up an acronym. Next time you hear this word, remember it is purely a Nigerian lingua liken to broken English.

Implementation

The term "Implementation" is synonymous with "execution". To execute means to take action or make a decision. In other words, implementation refers to the process of putting a decision into effect or execution. The work of execution of decisions or policies is vested solely on the executive arm of the government.

President Muhammadu Buhari Administration

The President Muhammadu Buhari administration began on May 29, 2015, being Nigeria's Democracy Day and the day he was sworn into office as the President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria following his election in the General Elections of that year. The first tenure of President Muhammadu Buhari lasted for four (4) years, from 2015 to 2019. President Muhammadu Buhari was re-elected as the President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and was sworn into office again on May 29, 2019. The second tenure of the president lasted for another four (4) years, from 2019 to 2023. President Buhari had two consecutive tenures in office of eight (8) years of administration in Nigeria.

7. Methodology

The qualitative survey research design was adopted because the study involves longitudinal investigations. "A longitudinal survey study involves examining survey responses over a certain timeframe to investigate whether there is any change in your variables of interest. In such a design, your survey needs to be administered at least twice—once at the start and at the end of the timeframe. You can also choose to administer it in the middle of a time frame. As such, both primary and secondary methods of inquiry were used. (ABS, 2021 in Udoh *et al.*, 2024). The primary data were basically from personal observations and interviews, while the secondary data were drawn from relevant text books, journals, newspapers, and the internet.

8. Theoretical framework:

Pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories

Introductory remarks:

A new theory propounded by Dr. Unwana-Abasi Udoh in 2023 was adopted in the study. The twofold or twin theories called pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories are theories for the distribution of government resources. The theories offer the managers of government resources two vital contemplations and scenarios in the sharing of government resources or public goods. They are postulated using basic natural resources, such as pawpaw/papaya and pineapple fruits. Pawpaw or papaya (botanical name) as well as pineapple fruits are agricultural products and are considered most appropriate when they are fully ripped for use in demonstrating the sharing processes. These thoughts, which are supported by Basic Resources Theory (Udoh, 2017), are advanced in an attempt to resolve the surrounding issues on the

concepts of equality and equity in the sharing of national and state resources in Nigeria, in particular, and around the globe in general.

The pawpaw/papaya theory has a single sharing stream, whereas the pineapple formula has two variances: the vertical and horizontal perspectives. The case in point is that, with fiscal federalism in mind, which places a premium on how financial resources of government are shared among the federal, state, and local government areas, the pawpaw/papaya theory represents equality, fairness, and justice on the one hand, while the pineapple theory represents equity and shrewdness on the other, respectively. In Udoh *et al.* (2018), the idea of fiscal federalism has received the endorsement of John Rawls' theory of justice, whose basic assumption concerns "the socially just distribution of goods in a society." A cursory and critical observation reveals that adopting the pineapple theory in financial sharing among tiers of government is to attempt some level of subtlety and shrewdness towards the lower levels of government by the higher level of government. This is so due to the assumption that pineapple does not ripen around the entire fruit equally at the same time, unlike pawpaw/papaya. This implies that without any careful observation on the use of the pawpaw/papaya approach in the financial sharing among tiers of government, the system or the process offers total fairness, equality, and justice among all levels of government. The reason is also based on the assumption that pawpaw rips around the entire body equally, at the same time, unlike pineapples, where any consumer who picks any part of the fruit must enjoy total sweetness.

The author therefore assures that the proper use of pawpaw theory is an antidote for a peaceful and harmonious coexistence of all the component parts of a nation or state, even though it may generate bad blood among the richer components whose greater goods may serve the greater happiness of the less-rich components. Whereas, the author warns that the use of pineapple theory can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by the component parts of a nation or state, except the horizontal variance of the pineapple theory is adopted instead of the vertical stream. These theories are authenticated by Udoh, U.S. (2014), Udoh, U.S. (2017), Udoh, U.S. *et al* (2017), Mboho, K.S. *et al* (2018), and Udoh, U.S. *et al* (2018).

Pawpaw/Papaya Theory

Udoh (2024) postulates that Pawpaw/Papaya Theory represents **equality, fairness, and justice**. The major assumption of pawpaw/papaya theory is that if pawpaw is peeled and sliced into smaller, but equal parts and into a bowl, it is argued that because the fruit rips around the entire body equally, at the same time, therefore, a consumer who picks any part of the fruit will enjoy the same sweetness that all other parts of the fruit contain. Based on this premise, the author opines that if financial

operators adopt Pawpaw/Papaya Theory as a guiding principle or as their sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to the component parts of the nation or state, that the action will be equality, fairness, and justice. In this theory, therefore, the consumers do not need to know exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail and what part of the bowl the different parts were shuffled. The fact in point is that all parts of pawpaw/papaya give an equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to consumers.

From the above assumption, if the sharers of government finances or public goods, the component parts of the nation, states, or LGs do not need any form of carefulness to know exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail and what part of the bowl the different parts were shuffled. This is because the sharing process with Pawpaw/Papaya depicts quality, fairness, and justice. The reason being that pawpaw/papaya rips around the entire body equally, at the same time. Therefore, consumers need not be circumspect in making choices on what parts of the fruit they have to consume. But, adversely, the richer parts of the federation stand a chance of generating greater resources for the greater good of the less-rich parts, as the official sharing parameters of government resources, like population, land mass, ecological issues, derivation, etc., may be ignored in an attempt to sympathise with those other parts of the federation to equally keep them afloat. That is why in some federations, monies are taken from richer states to finance poor ones, particularly by paying their staff salaries and pensions.

Pineapple Theory

Udoh (2024) further propounded the Pineapple Approach as representing **equity** and **shrewdness**. The major assumption of pawpaw/papaya theory is that if pineapple is peeled and sliced into smaller, but equal parts and into a bowl, it is argued that because pineapple does not ripe around the entire fruit equally, at the same time, a consumer has to pick the head of the fruit in order to enjoy the total sweetness that the fruit contains. Otherwise, picking the fruit's tail will leave the consumer with a soaring tongue instead of sweetness. Based on this premise, the author argues that if financial operators adopt Pineapple Theory as a guiding principle or as their sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to the component parts of the nation or state, that the action will be equity and shrewdness. In this theory, therefore, it is only the person who dressed the pineapple that knows exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail and what part of the bowl were the different parts shuffled. The fact in point is that not all parts of pineapple fruit give equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to the consumers.

From the above assumption, there are two streams to the explanation of the pineapple theory. One is the **vertical** and two is the **horizontal** sharing formulae. In the **vertical**

sharing formula, the fruitier of the resources first of all divides the pineapple vertically into two equal parts, from head to tail, before chopping the fruit into consumable sizes. The consumable pieces are placed and shuffled in a bowl before consumers are made to partake in eating the fruit. The argument is that because pineapple does not ripe around the entire fruit equally, at the same time, a consumer must pick the head of the fruit in order to enjoy the total sweetness that the fruit contains. Otherwise, picking the fruit's tail will leave the consumer with a soaring tongue rather than total sweetness. This implies that, despite the official sharing parameters of government resources, like population, land mass, ecological issues, derivation, etc., government resources can also, first of all, be shared equally. The equitable distribution of public goods is imbedded with subtle shrewdness and can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by the component parts of a nation or state.

But, in the **horizontal sharing formula**, the fruitier of resources divides the pineapple horizontally into two parts before chopping each part of the fruit into consumable sizes. The consumable pieces are placed in two separate bowls and shuffled before consumers are made to partake in eating the fruit, first from the bowl where the tail of the fruit was shuffled, before eating the fruit in the second bowl that the head of the fruit was sliced into. In the horizontal sharing formula, consumers have an equal chance to get a feel for the different tests in the two bowls.

Application of the theories to the study

In 2023, Dr. Unwana-Abasi Udoh, a lecturer in the Department of Public Administration at Akwa Ibom State University, propounded the pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories, which offer two intriguing scenarios in the sharing of government resources or public goods. The theories are postulated using natural substances, such as pawpaw/papaya and pineapple fruits. Pawpaw (papaya, botanical name) and pineapple fruits are agricultural products that are considered most appropriate for use in demonstrating the sharing processes of any sort, particularly government resources.

The case in point is that, with fiscal federalism in mind, which places a premium on how financial resources of government are shared among the federal, state, and local government areas or individuals, the pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories represent equality, fairness, and justice on the one hand, and equity and shrewdness on the other, respectively. A cursory and critical observation will reveal that adopting the pineapple theory in financial sharing among tiers of government is to attempt some level of subtle cheating on the lower levels of government by the higher level of government. The reason is based on the assumption that pineapple does not ripen around the entire fruit equally at the same time, unlike pawpaw/papaya. But, without

any careful observation on the use of pawpaw/papaya theory in the financial sharing among tiers of government or individuals, there is total fairness, equality, and justice among all levels of government. The reason is also based on the assumption that pawpaw rip around the entire body equally, at the same time, unlike pineapples. In summing up, estacode is not given to everybody in government who wants to embark on foreign travel. The reason is that not all applications will be approved. Some government officials are better connected to the powers that be than others. As a result, their applications will receive more immediate attention than others. That is where **equity** and **shrewdness** come into play.

9. Review of Related/Empirical Literature

Public finance

Atkinson et al. (1980) assert that public finance is the study of the role of the government in the economy. But, according to Blinder et al. (1974), public finance is the branch of economics that assesses the government revenue and government expenditure of the public authorities and adjusts one or the other to achieve desirable effects and avoid undesirable ones. In his original and edited works on public finance, Buchanan ([1967] 1987) provides the purview of public finance and considers it to be threefold, consisting of governmental effects on: the efficient allocation of available resources; the distribution of income among citizens; and the stability of the economy. Whereas economist Jonathan Gruber in Musgrave (1999) has put forth a framework to assess the broad field of public finance. Gruber suggests that public finance should be thought of in terms of four central questions: when should the government intervene in the economy? To which there are two central motivations for government intervention: market failure and redistribution of income and wealth. How might the government intervene? Once the decision is made to intervene, the government must choose the specific tool or policy choice to carry out the intervention (for example, public provision, taxation, or subsidization). Ferguson (1961) corroborates.

The government can pay for spending by borrowing (for example, with government bonds), although borrowing is a method of distributing tax burdens through time rather than a replacement for taxes. A deficit is the difference between government spending and revenues. The total public debt represents the accumulation of deficits over time. Deficit finance allows governments to smooth tax burdens over time and provides them with a crucial fiscal policy tool. Deficits can also limit successor governments' options. There is also a difference between public and private finance; in public finance, the source of income is indirect, e.g., various taxes (specific taxes, value-added taxes), but in private finance, the source of income is direct.

Public financial management:

In Udoh (2024), public financial management (PFM) is a central element of a functioning administration, underlying all government activities. It encompasses the mechanisms through which public resources are collected, allocated, spent, and accounted for. As such, PFM processes comprise the whole budget cycle, public procurement, audit practices, and revenue collection. Sound, transparent, and accountable public financial management is a key pillar of governance reform and is of vital importance to provide citizens with excellent quality public services, as well as to create and maintain fair and sustainable economic and social conditions in a country. The researcher further stated that PFM involves highly complex technical tasks and processes, including macroeconomic forecasting, budget allocation, accounting, and auditing. The complexity of such processes limits public scrutiny and provides many opportunities for corruption. The risk of corruption varies between and within the different stages of the budget process. Although corruption primarily manifests itself in forms that involve illegal money transfers at the budget execution level, other steps in the budget process may create opportunities for corruption at other stages of the PFM process, such as budget formulation, budget approval, accounting, and reporting or audit stages.

In the author's opinion, PFM reforms have typically focused on achieving and securing overall economic and fiscal stability, allocative efficiency, and operational efficiency. To this end, PFM reforms mostly prioritise technical approaches to improve the performance of the PFM systems, including through the integration, modernisation, and automation of PFM processes, revenue collection, public expenditure management, and procurement systems. While these reforms are not primarily aimed at curbing corruption, there is a broad consensus that they can help prevent and detect misuse of public resources through streamlined processes, increased transparency, and stronger oversight. In conclusion, the scholar believes that recent PFM reform trends call for moving beyond technical reforms and paying more attention to transparency, accountability, and public participation in PFM. Global initiatives, such as the Open Government Partnership, the Global Initiative for Fiscal Transparency (GIFT), and the International Budget Partnership are working for this purpose.

Estacode

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RMAFC in Keyamo (2015) had said that public office holders often abused the remuneration package, leading to the commission being criticised for fixing high amounts for allowances. “Perhaps the most challenging issue the Commission faces is the abuse by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package for political, public, and judicial office holders,” the commission stated.

“This has left the general public with the impression that the Commission fixed jumbo pay for political, public, and judicial office holders in spite of several clarifications by the Commission in the media on the matter,” it added. However, with the temporary ban on government sponsorship of official travels, the Federal Government has shown its resolve to not only embark on monetary tightening but also fiscal management.

Here are what Nigerian ministers, senators and others get as estacode per night for foreign trips:

Estacode per night for Nigerian government officials

S/No.	Designation	Amount in Dollar (\$)
1	Minister	\$900
2	Minister of State	\$900
3	Special Adviser	\$800
4	Director General of MDA	\$900
5	Chief Justice of Nigeria	\$2,000
6	Justices of Supreme Court	\$1,300
7	Appeal Court President	\$1,300
8	Judges of Courts	\$1,100 / \$600
9	Senate President	\$1,300
10	Dep Senate President	\$1,100
11	Senators	\$950

12	House of Rep Speaker	\$1,200
13	Deputy H of R Speaker	\$1,000
14	House of Rep Members	\$900
15	Commissioners	\$600
16	Special Advisers (State)	\$500
17	DG/Perm Secs (State)	\$500
18	House Assembly Speaker	\$700
19	Dep House Speaker	\$650
20	House Members (State)	\$600
21	LGA Chairman/Vice	\$450
22	Supervisory Councilors	\$400
23	LGA Special Advisers	\$400
24	LGA Legislative Leaders	\$225
25	Dep LGA Leg. Leaders	\$220
26	Councilors of LGA	\$210

Source: *Keyamo (2015), NCAA pivotal to Nigeria's 71% score in aviation security audit - Achimugu*

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Summary of International Trips by former President Muhammadu Buhari

Jasmine (2016) has provided a summary of the countries President Muhammadu Buhari of Nigeria has visited as President but tabulated by the researcher. According

to Jasmine (2016), there are two trips that he made to the United Kingdom, one on his official vacation and one for medical treatment, that are included in this list.

S/No.	Countries visited	Number of visits
1	Belgium, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Egypt, Guinea-Bissau, India, Iran, Japan, Liberia, Mali, Malta, Mauritania, Netherlands, Russia, Rwanda, Poland, Portugal, South Korea, Spain, Sudan, Togo, Turkey	1 each
2	Benin, China, Côte d'Ivoire, Equatorial Guinea, Germany, Jordan, Morocco, Qatar	2
3	Chad, Ghana, Kenya, Niger, South Africa, The Gambia, United Arab Emirates	3
4	Senegal	4
5	Ethiopia (6), France (5), Saudi Arabia (5), United Kingdom (5), United States (11)	6, 5, 5 5, 11, respectively.

Source: (Jasmine, 2016; but, tabulated by Researcher, 2024).

2015

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2015.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	Niger	Niamey	3 June	Anti-Boko Haram Summit	See also: Boko Haram insurgency
2	Chad	N'Djamena	4 June	State Visit	See also: Boko Haram insurgency
3	Germany	Munich	7-8 June	42 nd G7 Summit	See also: Group of Eight
4	South Africa	Johannesburg	12-13 June	25th African Union Summit	See also: African Union
5	United States	Washington, D.C.	19-23 July	State Visit	
6	Cameroun	Yaoundé	29-30 July	State Visit	See also: African Union
7	Benin	Cotonou	2-3 August	Independence Celebration	
8	Ghana	Accra	7 September	State Visit	
9	France	Paris	14-16 September	State Visit	
10	United States	New York City	24-29 September	70th session of the United Nations General Assembly	
11	India	New Delhi	26-30 October	<u>Third India Africa Forum Summit</u>	See also: <u>India–Nigeria relations</u>

12	Sudan	Khartoum	30 October	State Visit	
13	Iran	Tehran	22-24 October	3rd Gas Exporting Countries Forum	
14	Malta	Valetta	28-30 November	2015 Commonwealth Heads of Government summit.	
15	France	Paris	30 November– 1 December	<u>Paris Conference of Parties 21</u>	
16	South Africa	Johannesburg	4-5 December	China Africa summit	See also: China– Nigeria relations

Source: (*Jasmine*, 2016; but, tabulated by *Researcher*, 2024).

2016

The following is a list of worldwide presidential trips made by Buhari in 2016. Buhari made a journey to the United Kingdom in February 2016 and June 2016; however, they were not in an official capacity and were for normal medical exams.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	Benin	Cotonou	8 January	11th summit of the Heads of State of the Niger Basin Authority	See also: Niger Basin Authority
2	United Arab Emirate	<u>Abu Dhabi</u>	17-20 January	World Future Energy Summit	
3	Ethiopia	Addis Ababa	26 January	26th Summit of African Union Heads of State/ Government.	
4	Kenya	<u>Eldoret,</u> <u>Nairobi</u>	27-29 January	State Visit	See also: Kenya– Nigeria relations
5	France	Strasbourg	2-4 February	Official Visit	
6	Egypt	Sharm E l- Sheikh	18 February	Sharm el-Sheikh 'Africa 2016'	
7	Saudi Arabia	<u>Riyadh, Jeddah,</u> <u>Mecca, Medina</u>	22-27 February	State Visit	
8	Qatar	Doha	27-28 February	OPEC Meeting	See also: Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries
9	Equatorial Guinea	Malabo	14 March	State Visit	
10	United States	Washington, D.C.	30 March - 3 April	4th Nuclear Security Summit	
11	China	Beijing	11-14 April	State Visit	
12	United Kingdom	London	13-15 May	Anti-Corruption Summit	

13	Chad	N'Djamena	8 August	Inauguration of Idris Deby	See also: 2016 Chadian presidential election
14	Kenya	Nairobi	27-28 August	Tokyo Conference on Africa	
15	United States	New York City	11-15 September	Seventy-first session of the United Nations General Assembly	
16	Germany	Berlin	13-16 October	State Visit	
17	Morocco	Marrakesh	14-18 November	United Nations Climate Change conference	
18	Senegal	Dakar	5-7 December	Third Dakar International Forum on Peace and Security in Africa	
19	The Gambia	Banjul	13 December	ECOWAS Summit	See also: 2016 Gambian presidential election

Source: (*Jasmine*, 2016; but, tabulated by *Researcher*, 2024).

2017

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2017. In January, May, and September 2017, Buhari travelled to the United Kingdom; however, they were not in an official capacity and were for routine medical checkups.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	Ghana	Accra	7 January	Inauguration of Nana Akufo-Addo	See also: 2016 Ghanaian general election
2	The Gambia	Banjul	13 January	ECOWAS Mediation Meeting	See also: 2016-17 Gambian constitutional crisis
3	Mali	Bamako	13-14 January	27th Africa France Summit	
4	United States	New York City	17-20 September	Seventy-second session of the United Nations General Assembly	
5	Turkey	Ankara, Istanbul	18-22 October	State Visit	See also: Nigeria-Turkey relations
6	Côte d'Ivoire	Abidjan	28-30 November	5th EU -AU summit	
7	Jordan	Amman	1-4 December	Summit	

Source: (*Jasmine*, 2016; but, tabulated by *Researcher*, 2024).

2018

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2018.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	Ethiopia	Addis Ababa	28-30 January	30th Summit of African Union Heads of State and Government.	
2	United Kingdom	London	19-20 April	<u>2018 Commonwealth Heads of Government Meeting</u>	See also: <u>Commonwealth of Nations</u>
3	United States	Washington, D.C.	28 April – 4 May	Working Visit	See also: <u>Nigeria–United States relations</u>
4	Morocco	Rabat	10-11 June	Working Visit	See also: <u>Nigeria–Morocco relations</u>
5	<u>Mauritania</u>	<u>Nouakchott</u>	30 June – 3 July	31st Summit of African Union Heads of State and Government.	
6	<u>Netherlands</u>	<u>The Hague</u>	15– 18 July	20th Anniversary of the <u>International Criminal Court</u>	
7	Togo	<u>Lomé</u>	29 July	ECOWAS-ECCAS Summit	
8	China	Beijing	1-7 September	7th Summit of the Forum on China – Africa Cooperation	
9	United States	New York City	23-29 September	<u>Seventy-third session of the United Nations General Assembly</u>	
10	France	Paris	10-16 November	1st Paris Peace Forum	
11	<u>Poland</u>	<u>Krakow</u>	2-3 December	Summit	
12	Niger	Niamey	25 December	60th proclamation anniversary of Niger	

Source: (Jasmine, 2016; but, tabulated by Researcher, 2024).

2019

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2019. Between May 16–21, Buhari made a personal trip to Saudi Arabia to attend Lesser Hajj.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	Senegal	Dakar	2 April	Inauguration of <u>Macky Sall</u>	See also: <u>2019 Senegalese presidential election</u>
2	Jordan	Amman	4-7 April	World Economic Forum Summit	
3	United Arab Emirate	Dubai	7 – 10 April	Summit	
4	Chad	N'Djamena	13 April	Working Visit.	
5	<u>Saudi Arabia</u>	<u>Jeddah</u>	29 – 30 May	Summit	
6	Japan	Yokohama	28–30 August	Tokyo International Conference on African Development Summit	
7	<u>Burkina Faso</u>	<u>Ouagadougou</u>	14-15 September	ECOWAS Summit	
8	United States	New York City	21-26 September	<u>Seventy-fourth session of the United Nations General Assembly</u>	
9	<u>South Africa</u>	Pretoria	2-4 October	State Visit	
10	Russia	Sochi	21–23 October	Working Visit	1 st Russia-Africa Summit
11	<u>Saudi Arabia</u>	<u>Riyadh</u>	29-30 October (Buhari remained in Saudi until 1 November)	Summit	

Source: (*Jasmine*, 2016; but, tabulated by *Researcher*, 2024).

2020

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2020.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	United Kingdom	London	18-23 January	Summit	
2	Ethiopia	Addis Ababa	7-8 February	33rd Summit of African Union Heads of State and Government.	

Source: (*Jasmine*, 2016; but, tabulated by *Researcher*, 2024).

2021

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2021. In April 2021, Buhari visited the United Kingdom; however, they were not in an official capacity and were for routine medical checkups.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	United Kingdom	London	27-30 July	International Summit	Buhari attends the Global Education Summit on Financing Global Partnership for Education (GPE) 2021 to 2025.
2	United States	New York City	18-24 September	<u>Seventy-sixth session of the United Nations General Assembly.</u>	
3	Ethiopia	Addis Ababa	3-6 October	<u>Inauguration of Abiy Ahmed</u>	Abiy Ahmed's inauguration for a second term in office after the <u>2021 Ethiopian general election.</u>
4	Saudi Arabia	Riyadh	25-28 October	Working Visit	
5	France	Paris	10-13 November	Working Visit	Paris Peace Forum

Source: (*Jasmine*, 2016; but, tabulated by *Researcher*, 2024).

2022

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2022. Buhari made two trips to the United Kingdom in May and November 2022; however, they were not in an official capacity and were for routine medical checkups.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	The Gambia	Banjul	19 January	Inauguration of Adama Barrow	Adama Barrow's inauguration for a second term in office after 2021 Gambian presidential election.
2	Ethiopia	Addis Ababa	3-4 February	AU Summit	35 th Ordinary Session of the Assembly of Heads of State and Government of the African Union
3	Belgium	Brussels	17-18 February	EU Summit	<u>6th European Union–African Union Summit</u>
4	Kenya	Nairobi	2-3 March	Commemoration	Commemoration of the 50th Anniversary of the United Nations Environmental Program.
5	Ivory Coast	Abidjan	8-9 May	Conference of Parties	Attended The fifteenth session of the Conference of the Parties (COP15) of the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification

6	United Arab Emirate	Abu Dhabi	21 May	Working Visit	Condolence visit following death of President of the UAE Khalifa bin Zayed Al Nahyan.
7	Equatorial Guinea	Malabo	26-28 May	AU Summit	African Union Extraordinary Session of Assembly of Heads of State and Government.
8	Spain	Madrid	31 May - 1 June	Working Visit	State visit with Prime-Minister <u>Pedro Sánchez</u> and King <u>Felipe VI</u>
9	Ghana	Accra	4 June	ECOWAS Summit	2022 Second Ordinary Session of ECOWAS Parliament.
10	Rwanda	Kigali	22-26 June	CHOGM Summit	26th <u>Commonwealth Heads of Government Meeting 2022</u> .
11	Portugal	Lisbon	28 June - 2 July	Working Visit	Working visit with Marcelo Rebelo de Sousa and United Nations Ocean Conference.
12	Senegal	Dakar	6-7 July	IDA Summit	International Development Association (IDA) for Africa Summit.
13	Liberia	Monrovia	26 July	Working Visit	Liberia's 175th Independence anniversary celebrations.
14	United States	New York City	19-21 September	UN Summit	<u>Seventy-seventh session of the United Nations General Assembly</u> .
15	South Korea	Seoul	25-26 October	WHO Summit	1st World Bio Summit,
16	Niger	Niamey	25-26 November	AU Summit	African Union Summit on Industrialisation and Economic Diversification and the Extraordinary Session on African Continental Free Trade Area (AFCFTA).
17	Guinea-Bissau	Bissau	8 December	Working Visit	Amílcar Cabral Award awarded to Buhari by President Umaro Sissoco Embaló.
18			10-18 December	US Summit	Buhari attended the <u>United States–Africa Leaders' Summit 2022</u> along with 49 other African leaders.

Source: (Jasmine, 2016; but, tabulated by Researcher, 2024).

2023

The following is a list of international presidential trips made by Buhari in 2023.

S/No.	Country	Area Visited	Date(s)	Purpose(s)	Note(s)
1	Senegal	Dakar	24-26 January	Dakar 2 Summit	
2	<u>Ethiopia</u>	<u>Addis Ababa</u>	17-19 February	AU Summit	
3	Qatar	Doha	4-8 March	UN Summit	
4	<u>Saudi Arabia</u>	<u>Jeddah</u>	11-19 April	Working Visit	
5	United Kingdom	London	5-6 May	<u>Coronation of Charles III and Camilla</u>	

Source: (Jasmine, 2016; but, tabulated by Researcher, 2024).

Summary of findings

Based on the two assumptions in this investigation, two findings were made, as stated below: First of all, it was found that there had been challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders. Due to the above finding, the commission responsible for the management and implementation of estacode had wondered, “Perhaps the most challenging issue the commission faces is the abuse by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package for political, public, and judicial office holders,” the commission said (Udoh, 2024).

Secondly, the amount of estacode adoption in Nigeria during the President Muhammadu Buhari government between 2015 and 2023 was very high. That is the reason why Keyamo (2015) in Udoh (2024) was worried about the unfavourable perception that the public is holding about the fixing of jumbo pay to the recipients by the commission. “This has left the general public with the impression that the Commission fixed jumbo pay for political, public, and judicial office holders in spite of several clarifications by the Commission in the media on the matter.”

Conclusion

The researcher concluded that there had been challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders. According to the author, the level of implementation of estacode in Nigeria during the President Muhammadu

Buhari administration between 2015 and 2023 had been very high, leading to the bad impression that the public is holding about the fixing of jumbo pay to the beneficiaries by the commission. According to Udoh (2024), the situation has become worrisome to the extent that the government has, however, placed a temporary ban on further implementation of estacode for Nigerians traveling outside the country. "However, with the temporary ban on government sponsoring official travels, the Federal Government has shown its resolve to not only embark on monetary tightening but also fiscal management".

Recommendations:

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The federal government should set up machinery that will resolve all the challenging issues that the government faced in the form of abuses by stakeholders at both the national, state, and local government levels in the implementation of the approved remuneration package as an estacode for political, public, and judicial office holders.
2. The federal government should also ensure that going forward, the level of implementation of estacode in Nigeria, which had been very high during the President Mohammadu Buhari administration between 2015 and 2023, is moderated accordingly in order to reduce or totally exterminate the bad impression that the public is holding about the fixing of jumbo pay to the beneficiaries by the commission.

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